

Comparative Analysis of Frequency Support Provided by Grid-Forming and Grid-Following PVs

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Abstract—Widespread Photovoltaics (PVs), which are seen by a distribution network (or an isolated microgrid) as a constant power injecting source, can be detrimental to the frequency stability of the network. To assist in frequency regulation and response, the constant current control for a Distributed Energy Resource is substantially modified to provide inertial response within the low voltage network. PVs that deploy inertial control require an additional storage in order to cater to the demand supply balance. This approach is feasible for large scale PVs, however, rooftop PVs possess limited flexibility for additional storage. This paper studies case of a low-voltage networked microgrid with an appreciable PV penetration, in the presence of a diesel generator (DG) as a separate bus. A coordinated control for PV is designed in this paper, which can help in the transition in between the grid-forming mode to the grid-following modes (with the inertial control loop acting as the Phase locked loop), with the help of an auxiliary DC link voltage based control which is designed in a way that does not require any switching action.

Index Terms—Photovoltaics, Virtual Inertia, Microgrid

I. INTRODUCTION

Isolated microgrids prove to be a vital resource for provision of several accommodations, such as emergency power supply, short-term and long-term ancillary services to the utility grid point of connection [1]. The energy mix in isolated microgrids are generally led by the Distributed Energy Resources (DER), which work through proper control mechanisms to provide a reliable power flow, while maintaining the voltage and frequency limits. However, when the ratio of PVs are very high in an isolated microgrid, frequency stability becomes a matter of concern, as PV based inverters do not naturally provide inertia in the system. The main reason is that the PVs are considered as constant current injection sources, and the impact of such high PV penetration can reduce the synchronizing torque of the conventional generators [2]. Nevertheless, PVs have been providing voltage based ancillary services in terms of reactive power support and low voltage ride-through [3].

Frequency regulation in isolated networks with the help of voltage source inverters (VSI) is performed through the help of droop control [4]. However, droop controlled VSIs have limited inertial capabilities, because of the absence of

derivative term in the outer control loop. There are associated problems related to droop controlled inverters such as the permanent offset in voltage and frequency from the nominal values in the isolated mode, and also small-signal stability related concerns, because of the low frequency dynamics imposed by the outer loop controller [5], where the modes related to the aforementioned controller borders the right hand plane of the root loci. PV based Microgrids with no storage options with voltage and frequency control methodologies has been studied extensively [6], [7]. It is possible to have a day-time option for PVs, especially within an active distribution network to operate in the islanded mode for limited time, especially under low-load scenario. However, the functionality of droop controlled PVs are limited because of the lack of inertia, and frequent load switching can decrease the stability limits of the droop controlled PVs.

Inverters as virtual synchronous generators (VSG) or simply grid-forming inverters [8], acting within a microgrid has been studied in several literatures. VSGs are inverter based Distributed energy resources (DER) which can deliver synthetic inertia to the power system. The critical component that defines the VSG is the inertial controller derived from the swing equation (energy balance equation between the electrical and mechanical powers). [9] shows a design criterion for power sources with VSG deployment under the aegis of an isolated microgrid. When a PV is controlled through a VSG (acting as a grid-forming inverter), the PV power is expected to operate in the maximum power point (MPP), and an additional source, such as a battery or a super-capacitor is required for delivering/ absorbing the synthetic kinetic energy arising out of a potential imbalance in the AC and DC side powers. A similar work was reported in [10], where super-capacitor was employed for providing the inertial response. However, deployment of latter with a PV increases the cost of DER substantially.

The design of grid forming inverters for PV as part of an active distribution network includes the tuning of crucial parameters, which form the outer control loop. In general, a grid connected PV operating at MPPT employs a DC link voltage controller as the outer loop, and a current controller designed in the synchronous reference frame (d-q reference frame). The aforementioned controllers are generally tuned

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based on the inverter filter parameters, and the time-constant of the PWM switches. However, virtual inertia based controller parameters are generally system dependent because of the introduction of two parameters: Synthetic inertia constant, and the load damping constant. A small signal stability based parameter tuning approach was embarked in [11], for a virtual inertia PV system. Through Eigenvalue analysis, the virtual inertia effect was studied to test the system stability with different gains. However, the interaction was limited only to grid-forming PV(s), and a very simple test system was considered without taking into effect, the distribution network dynamics.

The main objective of this paper is to study the possibility of PV 'more' isolated microgrid to provide inertial response with the help of grid-forming controller. The main highlight of the paper is that the PV continues to provide inertial response in the isolated mode of operation, even in the worst case scenario such as a loss of a DG in the microgrid network. The designed controllers for the PVs ensure that the PVs share the loads in case of a load change while assisting in the frequency regulation. The black start capability of the Grid-Forming PVs is also shown in the presence of Induction Motor loads.

II. VIRTUAL INERTIA PROVISION BY PHOTOVOLTAICS

The control strategy of PVs working in the grid-forming control mode is described in this section. PV working in the grid-forming mode is responsible for controlling the voltage and frequency while working in the isolated mode. In the absence of energy storage, the grid-forming PV works in the power dispatch operation, and the additional degree of freedom provided through the outer control loop allows the PV to derate from its MPPT, and cater to the power-demand mismatch.

A. Philosophy

The control strategy for a grid-forming PV is based on the emulation of the second order synchronous machine dynamics, which is reflected in the outer control loop of the VSI control. The inner control loop comprises of the voltage and the current based controllers. The second order machine dynamics are bounded by the swing equation and the estimation of the load angle which can be seen in (1) and (2).

$$M \cdot \frac{d\omega}{dt} = P_m - P_e - D(\omega - \omega_0) \quad (1)$$

$$\delta = \int \omega \quad (2)$$

In the equations, the parameters, M and D denote the p.u. inertia and the load damping constants respectively. ω is the measured frequency in rad/sec at the VSI terminal, and ω_0 is the nominal frequency. The powers, P_m and P_e are the mechanical and electrical powers of the synchronous machine. In the PV context, these powers are replaced by the DC and AC powers. The values of the M and D are derived from the emulated kinetic energy of the PV. Since the PV does not possess the rotational energy, the same is extracted from the

Fig. 1. Comparison of Frequency response with different values of M and D

DC side capacitor dynamics, as can be seen in (3), (4) and (5).

$$\frac{1}{2} C_{dc} V_{dc}^2 = E_{dc} - E_{ac} \quad (3)$$

$$E_k = \int (P_{dc} - P_{ac}) dt \quad (4)$$

$$M = \frac{E_k}{S_{PV}} \quad (5)$$

The parameters, C_{dc} , V_{dc} , and S_{PV} are the DC link capacitor, the DC link voltage and the apparent PV power respectively. The load damping coefficient D is dependent on the load angle δ , the output impedance, and the inertia constant [11], and is instrumental in the outer control loop for stabilization of the frequency to the new set-point, especially in the islanded mode. Even though there is no direct approach to compute the value of D , especially in the context of PV based active distribution network, the value is estimated from the solution of the input-output relation of the active power to δ of the equations in (1) and (2). The relation between the damping factor, the load damping and the inertia constant is given in (6) and (7).

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{V^2 \cos \delta \omega}{M \cdot Z_o}} \quad (6)$$

$$D = \frac{2M}{\zeta} \omega_n \quad (7)$$

The different performance metrics of the inertia and damping coefficients for the PV can be seen in Fig.1, which shows a grid-forming PV within a network responding to a frequency related event. With the calculated values of M and D , the response to a load dip can be observed, and it can be noted that as the value of M is increased, and D is decreased, the undershoot is also decreased, however, this also leads to increased chattering in the measured frequency. The values of M and D are in seconds and rad/s/W respectively.

B. Control Design in Grid-Forming mode

The PV, as aforementioned works in the MPPT mode when connected to the utility grid, and hence, a DC link voltage controller is required for the generation of the power reference. In the grid connected mode, the PV continues to work in the MPPT, and hence the DC link voltage, V_{DC} follows the

Fig. 4. PV and Load Powers Over 24 Hour Horizon

for single phase, and 9kW for three phase. In similar lines, the loads are considered clustered, and single phase loads are accounted to be balancing into the equivalent three phase load. The schematic diagram for such a feeder is shown in Fig.3. The switches in the figure denote the islanding switches in case of a planned or an unintentional islanding. In this paper, the simulations will be carried out on the aforementioned test system. The load and the PV data for the test system is available for a 24-hour window in 15 minute intervals (Fig.4). For this study, no energy storage is considered. Therefore, the sole entity providing the frequency response are the hosted PV clusters. It can be seen from the figure that between the 1000 hours and 1200 hours, the PV power, P_{PV} is greater than the load power, P_{Load} , thus making an islanding possible, given that the PVs can work in the grid-forming mode.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The efficacy of the grid-forming and the grid-following controllers have been described in this section. As previously discussed, a comparative study will be performed for the PV with both grid-forming and grid-following modes of operation. The first and the third PV clusters are always operating in the grid-forming operation, whereas the second PV cluster is chosen between the two operational modes.

A. Network Operation from Grid connected Mode to Islanded Mode

The simulation assumes its start at nearly 1200 hours and considers simulations in seconds, the PV is operating in the grid connected mode at the beginning, and after a period of 15 sec, the grid is disconnected (as demonstrated in the simulations). The total loading during that time is nearly 50kW. In the absence of any storage or a diesel generator, the PV is able to cater to the loading, and also is able to cater to the changes in the loads and insolation, as the time progresses. Fig.5 shows the frequency measured at the three PVs. The insolation change is assumed to have similar effect on all the PVs, considering that all the PVs are installed at the same height, and have the same azimuths. It can be observed from Fig.5 that when the system of interest enters the islanded mode at the 15th sec, the first and the third PV have a frequency undershoot, whereas, the second PV has an overshoot in the frequency. This is because of the placement of the PVs and the R/X ratio of the lines. It can also be observed that when the insolation is increased, the frequency is slightly decreased

Fig. 5. Frequencies measured at the PV-VSI terminal(Grid-forming mode)

Fig. 6. Active Powers measured at the PV-VSI terminal

at the 20th sec. This is because the DC link voltage goes on the right of the PV-curve (value is increased) as the power is also increased, which is a similar phenomena, when the load is increased (at the 30th and 35th second). Therefore, by the virtue of the control law, the equivalent frequency is decreased upon an increase in the power or increase in the V_{DC} . However, upon a load increase, the V_{DC} starts coming towards its MPPT. The active powers measured at the PVs can be seen in Fig.6. The DC link voltages at the three PVs can be seen in Fig.7.

It is to be noted that in the figures, the first load change in 9kW at the 30th sec, and the second load change is 2kW at the 35th sec respectively.

Fig. 7. DC Link Voltage measured at the PV-VSI terminal

Fig. 8. Frequencies measured at the PV-VSI terminal (Grid-following mode)

Fig. 9. Comparison of different values of M and D : Power and Frequency measured

The second PV cluster is now modified to operate in the grid-following mode. It is observed that in this mode, even though the power sharing within the PVs is not compromised, which is with the help of the droop control, as was stated in (11), the behaviour of the frequency during a transient (grid outage at the 15th sec) is substantially changed, and the overshoot of the frequency is nearly 400% of the overshoot that is observed in case of the second PV operating in the grid-forming operation. However, within the islanded operation, the frequency response of the grid-following PVs are similar to the grid-forming PVs.

B. Black Starting of Network with IM Load

The operation of PVs working in the grid-forming mode while attempting to black-start the feeder of interest with different values of M and D are shown in figure 9. A Direct-On-Line starting induction motor (IM) load has been simulated at B10 in figure 3. The IM load is rated as a 10HP motor, with a line voltage $490 V_{LL}$ and an inertia constant of 0.04 sec. A speed based feedback is applied to the input torque by a factor of 3. The motor and a battery (parked EV) is turned on at the 6th second in the simulation, while the network is working in the islanded mode. The powers and frequency of the PV (P_{PV3}) operating closest to the IM are shown in the figure.

It can be observed from Fig.9 that in the presence of an IM load, and upon increasing the mechanical inertial constant in p.u., M , the oscillatory behaviour in both the active power response of the PV, as well as its frequency response is

decreased. The overshoot in the frequency is also decreased as a consequence in the increase in the value of M . It is to be noted that during the simulations, the value of D is deliberately not changed, as D mimics the droop coefficient ($Rad/sec/Watt$), and changing the value of D will alter the steady-state value of the frequency, while keeping the active power unchanged, as the droop coefficient for all the PVs for a particular simulation set is considered the same.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper studied the behaviours of grid-forming and Grid-following controls for PVs in a low voltage distribution network. It can be concluded stating that the PVs can operate without storage requirement and provide the necessary inertial response in a weak network. However, the placement of the PVs for the deployment of such controls remains a question, which is our scope for the future work. It can also be concluded that the placement of grid-following PVs within active distribution networks is also a possibility because of simpler controls compared to the grid-forming ones.

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